

Which Way to Go, Eurasia?

A non-citable editorial

IN FOLKLORE OF A CONSIDERABLE NUMBER OF PEOPLES, there is a persistent archetypal narrative. A protagonist that may be a knight, warrior, craftsman or just any other epical hero, sooner or later finds himself (himself much oftener than herself) at an ominous crossroads. There he sees a portentous label stating approximately the following: If you go to the left, you will lose you horse; if you go to the right, you'll lose your life; if you proceed straight, you'll be alive but forget yourself completely. Independently of the choice, our protagonist will undergo some or other critical peril. Modern Eurasia is not in the least different from the epical hero we talk about. It reached a dangerous, perhaps critical crossroads in its development. To preserve itself as a historical and social entity, it has to ask itself: Which Way to Go?

It was precisely this question that was posed by an outstanding group of scientist almost forty years ago. They are W. Sassin, A. Lovins, D. Meadows and P. Penczynski.¹ "Which Way to Go?" asked they not only Eurasian politicians and population that was severely and bitterly divided to Communists and Capitalists at the time (1977), but the whole humanity. They implied two ways of transformation of mode of life to sustainable development, "hard" and "soft." One of major questions to future generations was "Is it possible to design a strategy which at least for some time keeps both paths open?" Forty three years have passed, and it is obvious now that Eurasia chose neither. Perhaps, had Eurasian leading politicians and social activists been more prescient then, Eurasia would not have been at the terrible and foreboding crossroad stone in our days with the runes carved on it and predicting a catastrophic future to Eurasia independently of which way it chooses.

¹ Sassin, W., Lovins, A., Meadows, D. and P. Penczynski. 1977. Which Way to Go? *Options. A IIASA News Report*, no. 1 (Spring): 1-3.

A very brief and incomplete summary of what is awaiting Eurasia in the nearest several decades, may be formulated in such a list:

- 1) overpopulation that would be much more intense than in other parts of the world;
- 2) “spiral poverty,” or almost total impoverishment with desire to profit from its very fact;
- 3) emergence of different types of morality, re-thinking of phenomenon of a neighbour;
- 4) migration, problems of uncontrolled diasporas and refugee crises;
- 5) alteration of ethnic and racial composition of Eurasian nations;
- 6) change in understanding the level of income and style of life;
- 7) enormous growth of violence and crime;
- 8) social discontent;
- 9) healthcare crises and devastating epidemics beyond the COVID-19 pandemic;
- 10) infrastructural problems;
- 11) continuous change of law towards authoritarianism;
- 12) an huge default of energy systems of Eurasian countries;
- 13) a yawning abyss between debts and real income, whether measured by GDP or not;
- 14) incapability of masses to direct themselves and consequent constant search for “prophets” and “everyday leaders” who would teach masses how to live;
- 15) total cognitive and administrative fiasco at least clear in a rejection to support sustainability within Eurasian territory by political alliances of Eurasian countries.

The list, though far from being complete, is not a trifle itself.

Herodotus understood Eurasia as a combination of three parts, Europe, Asia and Africa (Libya) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Eurasia according to Herodotus.
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Herodotus’s words “I cannot conceive why three names, Asia, Europe and Africa... should ever have been given to a tract which is in reality one” clearly demonstrate that in the fifth century BC he considered Eurasia as an indivisible geographical and historical unity. However, unlike Herodotus, we have to include Subsaharan Africa in Eurasia too, although it looks a little whimsical for traditional economic geography and political theory. Dr-Ing Wolfgang Sassin, one of that brilliant team of researchers who in 1977 made their admonition to the world public, a co-founder of *Eurasian Crossroads*, has recently drew my attention to the fact that some 20 years ago Samuel Huntington in his book *Clash of Civilizations* disagreed with Fukuyama’s idea of *The End of History*. Huntington defined an Arc of Crisis, stretching from Afghanistan via the Muslim world down to East Africa. Since then, according to Dr Sassin, this “arc,” torn by fundamental religious and cultural contradictions, has extended way into Subsaharan Africa.² Moreover, countries of East and West Sudan understood as a historical and geographical unity gave almost as large population growth as India in terms of number of children in a family (Fig. 2) and may be regarded as a part of Eurasia for this reason too.

Fig. 2. Number of children in a common family.
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The problem of unlimited growth of human population is an acutest issue for Eurasia. Its Asian parts represent territories with highest density of population on earth (e.g. Shanghai, Bombay, Karachi, Tokyo, Dhaka) while European part suffers from uncontrolled migration of the poor into richer regions. Fig. 3-4 show that Eurasian input in the world population growth

² From the private scientific correspondence.

surpasses all other continents combined, if Subsaharan Africa is considered as a part of Eurasia.

Fig. 3. Population rate growth with division developed – industrialised countries (above) and continents (below).

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Fig. 4. World population density, people per km², for 2006.
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Unlimited growth of population in Eurasia begets all other woes listed above, poverty, high level of crime, mutual enmity on one side and idleness and parasitism on the other. During the last decade, Near and Middle East elaborated their own way of overcoming their regional overpopulation, migration to European Union as a safe haven (Fig. 4). Multiplied by the official ideology of European bureaucracy, i.e. ideology of repentance for the old period of colonialism, migration led to several administrative and infrastructural collapses in European Union, the main of which was so-called refugee crisis of 2015.

Wolfgang Sassin recently pointed out that Oswald Spengler in his *Der Untergang des Abendlandes* reacted to the competition of England, France, Russia and the latecomer Germany before and during World War I. This sociologist had no chance to see the fall of the Empires of Great Britain and France, nor had he a chance to analyse the Duopole USA and its tributaries on the one side and the Soviet Union and its mental “colonies” on the other. Now the process of this duopole dissolving is still in force since the collapse of the Soviet Union. At the moment slogan “America First!” indicates the dissolution of the collective “West,” the remainder of that duopole, as the main competitor of USSR. To really understand in which situation “mankind” is at the beginning of the 21st century, we have to go back to the origins of agriculture and the conflict this evolutionary step caused relative to those who depended on a given creation.³

³ From the private scientific correspondence.

Fig. 4. Migration routes in the world. Red: sources of migration. Blue: destinations of migration. Yellow lines: the major migration routes. It is clearly observable that Eurasia is characterised by the highest level and intensity of migration.

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If the modern EU may be compared with the Roman Empire in geographical and political dimensions, it becomes incontestable that Eurasia is a very unstable rhapsody of countries, societies, social groups and individuals – definitely not system – on the whole. If no clear self-determination of its European part has been made in the nearest future in regard to refugees and migration floods, EU may be doomed due to the novel Barbarian invasions, as the Roman Empire fell some one and a half thousand years ago because of the uncontrolled substitution of the Roman population by representatives of the “wild” Barbarian tribes, Goths, Vandals, Huns, Sarmatians and many else.

Intensities, volumes and directions of migration routes are further explicated in Fig. 5. Throngs of migrants from Near/Middle East, Mediterranean region and Subsaharan Africa into EU are marked as “those who are in need” by the European political mainstream. EU is at the ominous crossroads. It will repudiate either its official ideology of the comptroller of the poor regions of Eurasia or its wholeness – the Brexit has lately demonstrated it convincingly.

Fig. 5. Major migration intensities, volumes and routes.

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China and Russia as large territory states are in a better situation in no way. They are also at their crossroads. People Republic of China's population that counts some 1.7 billion people and Russian severe depopulation of Russian Far East will soon create the situation when Russia may cede its huge Siberian and Far East territories to those who need where to live, China, Japan, Korea. The complete absence of any consistent managerial strategy of Russian government in Russian Far East may make this process even smoother and

sooner. A diplomatic, national and military conflicts in the Far East may be inevitable, if the current perilous *status quo* continues for several decades to come. They may become even more dangerous than the current notorious and much talked-about USA – PRC political conflict. New Port Arthurs and Daman islands may start to loom on the horizon unexpectedly.

An additional factor stimulating internal and external struggle in Eurasia is the “spiral” poverty. Huge throngs of penniless and indigent individuals are propagating with a largest contribution to Eurasian overpopulation, with new hordes of their children and grandchildren even needier than themselves. Devoid of any hope and livelihood in their own lands devastated by internal conflicts, civil wars and terrorism, these masses sally forth to “promised lands” of European Union and hopefully United Kingdom to “conquer” them economically and socially, just as Spanish conquistadors did several centuries ago sailing to the New World of Americas with an hope to conquer it militarily. Without an habit of hard working to earn their sustenance, being indulged by the official EU ideology of “help for nothing,” these refugees’ activities en masse may provoke an implosion of EU or its transformation to an awful state of affairs brilliantly described by Harry Harrison in his *Make Room! Make Room!* (Fig. 6), when even artificial food would not suffice to feed al people, and they would turn to cannibalism. Such prophetic books are hardly ever laid upon the tables of leading Eurasian politicians. During the nearest decades, the population of Eurasia will scarcely build islands in the middle of oceans surrounding it or make uninhabited deserts of Takla Makan and Gobi appropriate for living, to settle several future billions of homo sapiens to be born by 2050. Therefore, Harrison’s dystopia may become a nightmare that would come true one unexpected day.

Fig. 6. Harry Harrison and his dystopia *Make Room! Make Room!* that depicts the future of over-populated humanity in condensed yet verisimilar tints.

A separate topic is the place and role of religious beliefs in new order which Eurasia now enters. Migrants to EU bring Islam with them, voluntarily or coercively, deliberately or unconsciously. For them, Islam is a part of their life. In the situation of almost total secularism in Europe and voluntary rejection of Christian commandments, that may lead to omnipresent Islamisation of Europe during the next several decades. Will Michel Houellebecq be a prophet, after all?⁴ Will not only France, but many European countries be ruled by Muslim Presidents and Prime Ministers? Not less important is the question about the future role of Christianity, Judaism, Confucianism, Buddhism and Hinduism in the development of Eurasia. Some classic Eurasian thinkers of the twentieth century admitted that unification of Eurasia will be under the standards of Orthodox Christianity. Mongolian pan-Eurasianism commenced with Orthodoxy – Genghis Khan’s brother was a Christian. In the mid-twentieth century, by his own life feat St John of Shanghai (Fig. 7) clearly demonstrated that Orthodox Christianity may be an unifying and creative force for the majority of Eurasian nations and ethnic groups. Will it be so on a large scale?

Fig. 7. St John of Shanghai and San Francisco, the Wonderworker. His Eurasian congregation in 1950s included around 100,000 representatives of more than thirty nationalities.
© Holy Virgin Cathedral Joy of All Who Sorrow in San Francisco (USA)

⁴ In 2015, Michel Houellebecq published his novel *Soumission* in which a Muslim President Ben-Abbes comes to power in France and establishes Shariah legal and social system with polygamy and Islam as the French official religion.

The fact that Eurasia is currently precisely at the crossroads, led us, a group of similarly thinking persons, to establish a new scientific journal *Eurasian Crossroads* for discussing most urgent and up-to-date issues emerging from Eurasian political, legal and social oscillations around this crossroads. The Journal fits the scope of Area Studies category of social sciences. We invite all scholars who would like to understand and formulate the most appropriate ways of Eurasian development and possibly present them further as political initiatives.

I hope that the first issue will kick a fresh start to our discussion with notable contributions of Wolfgang Sassin (Austria), Igor Likhomanov (Russia), Lady Cecily Grey (United Kingdom) and Lucille Dupont (France).

**Respectfully yours,
Editor-in-Chief**

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